

Date of analysis

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2022-05-05 aged samples

Analyst Sara Norrehed, Elyse Canosa, Helena Berg

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Författare Helena Berg
Handläggare Elyse Canosa

Technical Photography Instrument Report

Sample

Objects: Mock-ups on Canvas and Melinex, respectively.

Unaged Canvas (VIS, calibrated.)

Unaged Melinex (VIS), calibrated.

Riksantikvarieämbetet

Artillerigatan 33
Box 1114
621 22 Visby

Tel 08-5191 8000

E-post riksant@raa.se

Hemsida www.raa.se

Org.nr 202100-1090

Purpose

Technical photography is used to visualize the crack formations at, and below, the surface for two mock-ups of Richard Berghs painting *Konstnärsförbundets styrelse* (Nationalmuseum) in order to sort out which pigments might generate cracks.

Instrument Parameters

Camera

Nikon D810 with UV-IR blocking filter removed. Shooting mode was set to M and ISO to 100. The camera was connected to a computer via cable and connected to a power source also via cable. Aperture (in general 5.6-8) and exposure may vary and is registered in the meta data for every image.

Lens

Nikon AF NIKKOR 50mm mounted with a CHOS Robertina filter set consisting of a filter holder, a VIS-, UV- and IR-filter (see specifications in the appendix). The filter holder screws onto the lens and the filters are attached by internal magnets.

Software

Digicam Control to control the camera during photography

Adobe Camera Raw and Bridge for basic edits like crop, color profile, sharpness, renaming etc.

Nip2 with Bm-workspaces, a plug-in from British Museum

Standards

McBeth color chart (color calibration)

Spectralon© (white reflectance standard)

Object-instrument placement

All sets of images were shot with the objects placed flat on a table with the camera mounted from above at a distance of 100 cm from the camera. The light sources had a 45-degree angle towards the objects.

Background

Generally, a non-reflective, non-luminescing background is used to place the object on. The grey paper inhibits luminescence in UV-light which disturb the visualisation of the object under UV-light, mainly due to reflections from the background. The objects were not allowed to move to another background.

Results

All images presented are post-processed using the Charisma process (see below).

Mock-up on Canvas

VIS

Unaged

Aged

IRR

Unaged

Aged

UVR

Unaged

Aged

UVL

Unaged

Aged

Mock-up on Melinex

VIS

Unaged

Aged

IRR

Unaged

Aged

UVR

Unaged

Aged

UVL

Unaged

Aged

Light sources

UV - 350-400nm

G. Engelbrecht UVA-366, Thanning, Germany

VIS 5500K - 450-750nm

K. Apature Amaran AL-528C, Shenzhen, China

VIS 3200K - 450-750nm

K. Apature Amaran AL-528C, Shenzhen, China

VIS/IR Halogen - 400-1000nm

Housing: Kaiser Studiolight 1000, Buchen, Germany

Bulb: Osram Superphot 1000W, Munich, Germany

IR - 775-875nm

Synergy 21 Allnet M30205, Munich, Germany

Filters:

UV Pass

325-375nm ~75%, >400nm 0%

CHSOS Robertina UV, Viagrande, Italy

UV/IR Cut

<375nm ~0%, 400-550nm ~85%, 700-900nm ~0%

CHSOS Robertina VIS, Viagrande, Italy

IR Pass

350-800nm 0%, 900nm 25%

CHSOS Robertina IR, Viagrande, Italy

Light and filter combinations

Light source	Filter	Image
VIS	VIS	VIS
VIS	IR	VIL
UV	VIS	UVL
UV	UV	UVR
IR	VIS	IRL
IR	IR	IRR

Post Processing

Post processing follows the method developed under the Charisma project by the British Museum (J. Dyer, G. Verri, J. Cupritt, Multispectral Imaging in Reflectance and Photo-induced Luminescence modes: A User Manual, 2013, Version 1.0, The British Museum/Seventh Framework Programme). Detailed descriptions and background of processing steps can be found in above mentioned manual. Below are some general descriptions of important steps in the post processing.

VIPS, Nip2 and bm-workspaces.ws

Nip2 is a graphical interface for the image processing system VIPS. During Charisma a certain protocol or "workspace" was developed to unify the post processing both in terms of making it nondependent on equipment but also to maximize the information gained from the images.

- **Flat field correction:** For every set of lightsources+filter a flatfield image is taken by placing a flat non-specular board in front of the object. The flatfield should be slightly out of focus and cover the entire field of view of the camera. Nip2 corrects the image for spatial inhomogeneities of the light source/s. This requires a white reflectance standard (Spectralon®).
- **Colour calibration:** This corrects the colours in the image by comparing them to a standard also visible in the image. This requires a MacBeth chart.

General descriptions of generated images (p.3-6 Charisma manual)

VIS (Visible)

Lightsource: Visible (LED panels)

Filter: Visible

Standard photography image, reflected light in the region of 400-700nm. This image is the reference point according to what we see with our eyes.

VIL (Visible-induced luminescence)

Lightsource: Visible (LED-panels)

Filter: IR

Records the emission of radiation in the IR region (700-1100nm) from the object when it is illuminated with visible light. This image is especially useful for visualising pigments like Han blue, Han purple and cadmium-containing pigments.

UVL (Ultraviolet luminescence)

Lightsource: UV

Filter: Visible

Records the emission of light in the visible region 400-700 nm from an object when it is illuminated with UV radiation. Used to investigate distribution of luminescent materials, such as some organic binders and dyes. Also some inorganic materials have luminescent properties, eg zinc oxide.

UVR (Ultraviolet reflectance)

Lightsource: UV

Filter: UV

The reflected radiation in the ultraviolet region 200-400 nm when the subject is illuminated with UV light. Especially useful to visualize coatings and varnishes (become light), UV light is generally absorbed at the surface of materials (surface looks dark).

IRR (Infrared reflectance)

Lightsource: Infrared

Filter: Infrared

Reflected infrared radiation from and object in the infrared region of 700-1100 nm when it is illuminated by IR light.

This type of image can be useful especially for underdrawings in paintings. Many materials such as organic dyes and binders become transparent under these conditions. Infrared radiation is usually highly penetrative.

False-colour reflected images

Combinations of IR and UV reflected images which can result in distinctive “false colours” that may help to visualize different materials.

UVRFC (Ultraviolet-reflected false-colour)

IRRFC (Infrared-reflected false-colour)